

Research outputs

A comparative assessment of Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Nigeria, Rwanda, Tanzania and Uganda

Research production across the seven countries is low, averaging around 10% of South Africa's.²

Yet median productivity per researcher is higher than the UK.^{1,2}

Most publications come from international research partnerships, but questions remain over whether partnerships are equitable.²

Research published in the reviewed countries is widely cited, indicating the value of international partnerships.²

University-business collaborations are an engine of growth, and many governments actively pursue it.⁴

Very few patents are filed in these countries: investments are needed for research to drive national innovation.³

This data comes from a needs assessment study of the research systems in seven African countries, produced for the UK Department for International Development. The full set of infographics and the underlying analysis is available at <http://bit.ly/SRIA2020>

1 UNESCO, "UIS Statistics," 2019: <http://data.uis.unesco.org>
 2 Scimago, "Scimago Journal & Country Rank," 2019: <https://www.scimagojr.com>
 3 World Intellectual Property Organisation, "Statistical Country Profile": https://www.wipo.int/ipstats/en/statistics/country_profile
 4 World Economic Forum, "Global Competitiveness Index 2017-2018" 2017: <http://reports.weforum.org/global-competitiveness-index-2017-2018/competitiveness-rankings>

